

Histopathological Study of Gall Bladder Lesions in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Introduction: Gall bladder is very important part of hepatobiliary system and cholecystectomy is most common procedure performed in gall bladder lesion. This study was done with a purpose to determine the group of histopathological lesions found in electively operated cholecystectomy specimens. Females in their forties are more prone to develop cholecystitis along with cholelithiasis. The gall bladder pathology ranges from chronic cholecystitis to highly lethal adenocarcinoma

Aims and Objective: This study was undertaken with a purpose to determine the frequency and classify different histopathological lesions encountered in cholecystectomy specimens in Dr. KNS Memorial Institute of Medical Sciences, Barabanki.

Material and Methods: This is a prospective study conducted on 200 cholecystectomy specimens received in the Department of Pathology of Dr KNS Memorial Institute of Medical sciences Barabanki, over a period of 18 months from January 2023 to June 2024. Clinical details and histopathological data were retrieved from the hospital records.

Results: There were 200 cases in total, consisting of 48 males and 152 females. Male: female ratio was 1:3.1. Age of the patients from 10 to 70 yrs with a mean age of 40 years. Maximum number of patients were in fourth decade of life (55%).

Conclusion: The outcome of this study suggest that females were found to be more commonly affected in all pathologies of gallbladder. We found chronic cholecystitis with cholelithiasis to be the most common histopathological diagnosis followed by cholesterolosis.

Keywords: Cholelithiasis, Chronic Cholecystitis, Cholesterolosis, Histopathological.

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Introduction

The Gall bladder is pear shaped hollow organ lies beneath the liver, measuring 7-10 cm long, 3-4 cm in width and its total capacity is 50 ml. It is very important part of the biliary system in our body, where the storage and concentration of bile takes place.

World -wide gallstones disease is a common health problem [1]. More than 95% of the biliary tract disease is attributed to Cholelithiasis. The gall bladder pathology ranges from cholecystitis to premalignant to malignant lesion.

Material and Method

This is prospective study which includes 200 cases of gall bladder specimens collected over a period of 18 months in the department of pathology, Dr Kailash Narayan Singh Memorial Institute of

medical Sciences from Barabanki region in Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. The study was conducted to reveal the various pathologies of Gall bladder which includes Cholecystitis (Chronic cholecystitis, Xanthogranulomatous Cholecystitis, Eosinophilic Cholecystitis, Follicular Cholecystitis), Cholesterolosis, Cholelithiasis, Dysplasia, Polyp and Malignancy.

The study included Histopathological samples of all gall bladder biopsies obtained in the cholecystectomy operations done over the period of 18 months. Cholecystectomy specimens fixed in 10% formalin were received. Gross examination findings, relevant clinical history and USG findings were noted. Multiple sections were taken from specimen submitted for processing by paraffin embedding. Appropriate numbers of section of 4-5

micron thick tissue sections were cut and stained routinely with Hematoxylin and Eosin. There was no inter-observer variability in any of the cases. Ethical committee approval was acquired and consent from the patients was taken in clinical surgical department before the surgical procedure.

Result

Total 200 cases of cholecystectomy specimens were analysed in the study over a period of 18 months from January 2023 to June 2024. The stained slides were analyzed microscopically and categorized into various pathologies like chronic cholecystitis, cholesterosis, acute cholecystitis, follicular cholecystitis, eosinophilic Cholecystitis, Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis, adenomatous polyp, dysplasia and malignancy.

Age and gender of patients: Maximum number of patients with gall bladder pathologies were seen in the age group of 31-40 years (55%) with mean age of presentation was 35.5years. The age wise distribution shown in Table 1.

Out of 200 cases, there were 48 males and 152 females with M:F ratio of 1:3.1. The sex- wise distribution shown in Table 2.

Maximum number of cases were of chronic cholecystitis with cholelithiasis which contribute to (55%) of total patients in the study, followed by 25 cases (12.5%) of cholesterosis, 10 patients (5%) of acute cholecystitis. Figure-1, Figure- 2.

There were 2 cases of (1%) Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis. 4(2%) cases each of eosinophilic and follicular cholecystitis and 2(1%) case each of adenomatous polyp and dysplasia.

The present study carried out in our institution showed gall bladder malignancy was seen only in 03(1.5%) cases which was diagnosed as adenocarcinoma. Figure-3.

Gall Stone association with different HPE Findings of Gall Bladder: Out of 200 cases maximum 177 cases (60.4%) of chronic cholecystitis having association with gall stone. 23 cases were of acalculous cholecystitis. Out of 3 cases of adenocarcinoma gall bladder, 1 case was associated with gall stone.

Table 1: Showing different Histopathological findings in different Age Group

Age	Chronic cholecystitis with cholelithiasis	Chronic-cholecystitis without cholelithiasis	Cholesterosis	Acute cholecystitis	Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis	Follicular cholecystitis	Follicular cholecystitis	Adenomatous polyp	Dysplasia	Adenocarcinoma
21-30 years	04	00	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
31-40 years	110	01	15	06	02	00	00	02	00	00
41-50 years	20	05	06	02	00	01	02	00	01	00
51-60 years	02	01	02	01	00	02	02	00	01	01
61-70 years	04	01	01	01	00	01	00	00	00	02
Total 200	140	08	25	10	02	04	04	02	02	03

Table 2: Showing different Histopathological findings in different Sex Group

Gender	Cholecystitis with cholelithiasis	Chronic-cholecystitis without cholelithiasis	Cholesterolosis	Acute cholecystitis	Follicular cholecystitis	Follicular cholecystitis	Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis	Adenomatous polyp	Dysplasia	Adenocarcinoma
Male	38 (19%)	01 (0.5%)	05 (2.5%)	02 (1%)	00 (0%)	00 (0%)	01 (0.5%)	01 (0.5%)	00 (0%)	01 (0.5%)
Female	102 (51%)	07 (3.5%)	20 (10%)	08 (4%)	04 (2%)	04 (2%)	01 (0.5%)	01 (0.5%)	02 (1%)	02 (1%)
Total	140 (70%)	08 (4%)	25 (12.5%)	10 (5%)	04 (2%)	04 (2%)	02 (1%)	01 (0.5%)	02 (1%)	03 (1.5%)

Table 3: Distribution of cholecystectomy specimen according to HPE findings

HPE	Number of cases	Percentage
Chronic cholecystitis with cholelithiasis	140	70%
Chronic cholecystitis without cholelithiasis	08	4%
Cholesterolosis	25	12.5%
Acute cholecystitis	10	5%
Follicular cholecystitis	04	2%
Eosinophilic cholecystitis	04	2%
Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis	02	1%
Adenomatous Polyp	02	1%
Dysplasia	02	1%
Adenocarcinoma	03	1.5%
Total	200	100%

Table 4: Gall stones association with different HPE Finding of Gall bladder

Gall bladder disease	Gall stones	Percentage
Acute cholecystitis (10 cases)	06	3%
Chronic cholecystitis	140	70%
Cholesterolosis	10	5%
Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis	00	0.0%
Follicular	02	1%
Eosinophilic	01	0.5%
Adenomatous Polyp	01	0.5%
Dysplasia	01	0.5%
Adenocarcinoma	01	0.5%
Total (200 cases)	160	81%

Figure 1: a. Gross- Gall bladder with multiple blackish stones b. Microscopy –(10x) Chronic cholecystitis
Chronic cholecystitis

Figure 2 a. Gross (Strawberry mucosa) b. Microscopy(40x lipid laden macrophages)
Cholesterolosis

Figure 3 a. Gross- Adenocarcinoma Gall bladder b. Microscopy 10x- Sheets of malignant cells infiltrating liver parenchyma

Adenocarcinoma- Gallbladder

Adenocarcinoma Gallbladder (40x)

Discussion

Total 200 cases of cholecystectomy specimens were studied during January 2023- June2024 period. The age of patients with gallbladder disease ranged from 10 to 70 years, and most commonly found in 4th decade.

The results of our study are similar to Pal et al [2], Rakesh BH et al [3] and Mohan et al [4] study, they found that 4th decade is most commonly affected age group.

However, Tamil selvi et al [5] and Vahini et al [6] found the maximum incidence of gall bladder disease 6th and 5th decade respectively.

There was 48 males and 152 female with Male/Female Ratio in our study of 1:3.1 which showed female were most commonly affected than males. The results are comparable to Pal et al, Khanna Ret al [7], Patil et al [8] and Mazium et al [9] study who

concluded M:F ratio was 1.2.7, 1: 4.8, 1: 3.2 ,1:2.3 respectively. However, Ye Rim Chang et al [10] study stated that males were most commonly affected than females.

In our study cholecystitis with cholelithiasis is the most common diagnosis, which is similar to Cyrus Dora et al [11] study, who found that chronic calculous cholecystitis was most common histopathological diagnosis. The term cholecystitis refers to a group of disorders that vary in clinical, pathogenetic and pathological characteristics. Characterization of inflammatory pattern helps the pathologists to confirm the diagnosis.

The incidence of cholesterolosis (25%) in our study was second most common lesion after chronic calculous cholecystitis, which was similar to Pathak R et al [12] study.

In our study cases of acute cholecystitis, mean age of patients with acute cholecystitis is 35.5 years. The

observation was also concurrent with previous study done by Glenn et al [13]. who reported. The frequency of acute cholecystitis was found 5% in our study, as Tadashi Terada [14] study showed 1.5% of cases of acute cholecystitis. Acute cholecystitis was diagnosed more in female as compared to males in our study, which is similar to study done by Kumar H et al [15].

In our study the 4-4 cases each of follicular and eosinophilic cholecystitis were discovered, accounting for 2% of total patient, with female predominance which is similar to study of Mahajan V.R et al [16].

Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis is uncommon inflammatory and destructive gall bladder process. In our study 2 cases was diagnosed as Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis and not associated with gall stone which is similar to Devi Beena et al [17].

The prevalence of adenomatous polyp is 1% in our study, however prevalence rate of adenomatous polyp were found to be 4.3%- 6.9% in Ake Andren study [18].

In our study 2 cases of dysplasia found in female with mean age of presentation was 50 year, similar to Mukhopadhyay et al [19] in which mean age of dysplasia was 52.5 years

In our study 03 cases of adenocarcinoma seen, male to female ratio was 1:2. Average age of gall bladder cancer was found 50-70 years in our study was similar to that of Perpetuo et al [20], however shukla et al [21] reported mean age of patient to be 50 years (range 40-60 year)

Gall bladder carcinoma is most common cancer of biliary tree and the 5th most common gastrointestinal malignancy. It is characterized by rapid progression and very high mortality rate. The incidence of gall bladder cancer varies by geographic region and racial ethnic group. The highest incidences are reported in Asian subcontinent, central Europeans, Native Americans of Mexican origin.

Conclusion-

The study concludes that females of age group 31-40 years usually undergo cholecystectomy. Chronic cholecystitis was the most common histopathological diagnosis followed by cholesterolosis, acute on chronic cholecystitis, polyps, adenocarcinoma and Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis. Routine histopathological examination of cholecystectomy specimens is important to detect non neoplastic lesions as well as neoplastic lesions and sometimes incidental gall bladder cancer. Hence, were commend routine histopathological examination of all gall bladder samples for timely diagnosis and quick intervention to reduce incidence of carcinoma gallbladder.

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